

An Ensemble Deep Learning Approach for COVID-19 Severity Prediction Using Chest CT Scans

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Abstract

Chest X-rays have been widely used for COVID-19 screening; however, 3D computed tomography (CT) is a more effective modality. We present our findings on COVID-19 severity prediction from chest CT scans using the STOIC dataset. We developed an ensemble deep learning based model that incorporates multiple neural networks to improve COVID-19 severity prediction. To address data imbalance, we used slicing functions and data augmentation. We further improved performance using test time data augmentation. Our approach, which employs a simple yet effective ensemble of deep learning-based models with strong test time augmentations, achieved results comparable to more complex methods and secured the fourth position in the STOIC2021 COVID-19 AI Challenge. Code is available online at: STOIC AI Challenge.

Keywords: COVID-19 severity, Automated medical diagnosis, Radiology, CT scans.

1 Introduction

COVID-19 has created a global health crisis with millions of cases and deaths reported worldwide. Timely and accurate COVID severity prediction is essential for effective clinical management and treatment. Deep learning has shown tremendous potential in the medical domain. Automating the severity prediction of COVID-19 based on deep learning can lead to improved clinical workflow, resulting in faster diagnosis and better prognosis for severe COVID-19 cases. While a large number of studies have utilized deep learning methods for COVID-19 prediction based on chest X-ray data, CT scans have been found to be more effective in detecting COVID-19 positivity and severity [Aswathy et al., 2021]. Previous studies have primarily focused on COVID-19 positivity prediction or improving feature extraction methods. However, limited work has been done on COVID-19 severity prediction using CT scans.

2 Material and Method

We employed an ensemble deep learning approach to predict COVID-19 severity in high-resolution 3D CT scans provided by the STOIC2021 COVID-19 AI Challenge [Boulogne, 2022]. The scans had a spatial resolution of 512×512 and a depth of 128 to 600 slices. To standardize the number of slices, we used a uniform sampling function, which samples 32 uniformly spaced slices from the slice dimension. The radiodensity is measured using Hounsfield Units (HU), ranging from -1024 HU to 3071 HU, and stored as 12-bit numbers [Glide-Hurst et al., 2013]. However, directly scaling these values to [0,1] results in low contrast images that make identification of COVID-19-related features difficult [J et al., 1995]. To improve contrast, we utilize

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Figure 1: The schematic overview of our method.

the lung window with a window width of 1500 HU and a window level of -600 HU [J et al., 1995]. To deal with data scarcity, we partitioned the training set into five random splits. ResNet18 and MobileNetV3 are used for prediction. The overview of our method is shown in Figure 1. For every split, each pre-processed slice S_i is passed through both the ResNet18 and MobileNetV3 encoder E to obtain feature vectors $z_i = f(S_i)$. The maximally activated features are selected along the slice dimension on the feature vectors of the slices as $z_j^{\max} = \max\{z_i\}_{i=1}^{32}$ where $z_i \in R^D$. Only z_j^{\max} feature vector is then used by the fully connected layer to predict COVID severity \hat{x}_s and COVID positivity \hat{x}_p . The two models are combined through an ensemble technique, where the probabilities from both models are averaged to obtain the final prediction. Finally, the probabilities obtained from all five splits are averaged together to get final prediction \hat{y}_s and \hat{y}_p .

A number of challenges were encountered while experimenting with STOIC dataset [Boulogne, 2022]. a) The publicly available subset of the STOIC dataset is composed of only 2000 subjects, training the model with such a limited data is highly challenging. To avoid overfitting, various image level augmentations: random rotations, random crops, random gamma adjustment, color jitter, median blur, multiplicative noise, and *mixup* were used. These augmentations led to improvements in our results (Table. 2). Furthermore, performance was improved by test time data augmentation (TTA) with center crop, crops around four corners, safe rotate. b) The publicly available sample of STOIC dataset is heavily imbalanced, with only 301 subjects identified as severe COVID cases. To ensure training stability, a balanced sampler is used to assign weights to samples in proportion to the inverse occurrence of their respective classes in the training set. It helped to prevent the model's bias to the majority class. c) In addition to implementation challenges, the submission limit was restricted to one per week.

3 Results and Discussion

All the models were trained for 100 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a weight decay of 0.0005. The binary cross-entropy with logits criterion was used for evaluation. The training hyperparameters included a batch size of 16, a learning rate of 5×10^{-4} with a decay of 0.5 every 40 epochs using StepLR. The STOIC dataset [Boulogne, 2022] comprises of CT scans from 10,735 subjects. For this challenge, the dataset has been divided randomly into a publicly available training set (2,000 subjects) released under the CC BY-NC 4.0 license, a test set ($\sim 1,000$ subjects) and a private training set (7,000+ subjects). The scans are in .MHA format and have a resolution of 512×512 with varying number of slices ranging from 128 to 600. The meta-data contains information about the subject's age and gender, with age ranging from 35 to 85 years and a gender distribution of 57.4% male and 42.6% female. The ground truth consists of two labels: COVID-19 positivity and COVID-19 severity. The primary evaluation criterion is COVID-19 severity Area Under the Curve (AUC). We experimented

with multiple algorithms on the public set as shown in Table 1, and chose the one that performed best on the public test set. We then used this algorithm on the qualification leaderboard (LB) test set. Based on the results obtained from the qualification LB, we were able to evaluate the generalization performance of the model and submitted the improved version to final LB. ConvNext Tiny [Liu et al., 2022] performed well on the public data set; however, when tested on the qualification LB, AUC severity dropped significantly to 0.748, indicating poor generalization performance. Alternative models were also investigated: 3D CNN, MobileNetV3 small, and the use of encoders as fixed feature extractors along with age and sex metadata. These did not improve the predictive performance. Building on our initial results from Table 1, we conducted further experiments with ResNet18 and MobileNetV3. To evaluate the impact of augmentations on the overall prediction, we experimented with four set

Table 1: Performance evaluation based on AUC Severity and AUC COVID on public STOIC subset [Boulogne, 2022].

Model	STOIC Public Data		Qualification LB	
	AUC Severity	AUC COVID	AUC Severity	AUC COVID
CNN	0.687	0.780	-	-
ConvNext	0.845	0.748	0.748	0.800
ResNet18	0.775	0.784	0.752	0.784
MobileNet	0.817	0.780	0.779	0.735

of augmentations. 1) Default: consisting of horizontal flip, random crop to 224×224 , random gamma and color jitter with brightness 0.5, contrast 0.5 and saturation 0.4. 2) Default + Strong: consisting of safe rotate with limit 30, median blur, and the default augmentations. 3) Default + Strong + Mixup [Zhang et al., 2017]: consisting of set 1, set 2 and mixup augmentation. The mixup function is applied to the batch of images and labels i.e. COVID severity and COVID positivity with $\alpha = 0.8$. It returns augmented images and mixed-up labels for both the classes respectively. 4) Default + Strong + Mixup + TTA: consisting of TTA, center crop, crops around four corners, safe rotate along -5, 10, +5. As shown in Table 2, the integration of augmentation further improved the performance. TTA proved to be effective and greatly complemented the other augmentation techniques, further enhancing the overall performance of the model. To select the best model for final LB submission, for each split,

Table 2: Impact of augmentation on AUC Severity.

Augmentation	Public data		Qualification LB	
	ResNet18	MobileNetV3	ResNet18	MobileNetV3
Default	0.775	0.817	0.752	0.779
Default + Strong	0.795	0.831	0.781	0.793
Default + Strong + Mixup	0.842	0.829	0.790	0.795
Default + Strong + Mixup + TTA	0.863	0.841	0.815	0.821

we created an ensemble of ResNet18 and MobileNetV3 with most effective augmentation as shown in Table. 2 and finally ensembled predictions from all five splits as described in Section 2.

4 Comparison with top methods on final LB and conclusion [Boulogne, 2022]

The first ranked team, pre-trained ConvNext [Liu et al., 2022] with MosMed [Morozov et al., 2020] for severity classification and UperNet [Xiao et al., 2018] with TCIA [Aerts et al., 2015] for lesion segmentation. It was followed by training on STOIC dataset using metadata and the output of both backbones as vectors. They used a 5-fold cross-validation and ensemble model for testing. Team 2, used two vision encoders pre-trained on iBot [Zhou et al., 2021] via self-supervised learning on plain slices and segmented lung regions. They concatenated the features with age and sex features and used logistic regression for predictions. Team 3, used a lung segmentation model and autodidactic pre-training on segmented images. The network’s output was combined with age and passed to a fully connected layer and finally ensemble of five models and TTA was

Table 3: Final leader board results: comparison with top ranked methods [Boulogne, 2022].

Model	STOIC Public Data	
	AUC Severity	AUC COVID
First	0.815	0.616
Second	0.811	0.845
Third	0.794	0.837
Fourth (our method)	0.787	0.829

used. In contrast to other methods, our approach did not use highly complex models with additional data sets. Despite its simplicity, our method is highly effective and competitive with the more complex techniques, as can be seen from Table 3. Unlike other methods, we did not use metadata for the final LB submission as it did not improve performance on the public data set. Despite observing the same phenomenon, other teams opted to include metadata in their final submission and it proved to be effective. If our approach had included metadata, it might have been ranked among the top three teams in the competition.

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